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Author Note

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The study data and materials will be shared openly as part of the publication of the article. As

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the ethics committee at the University of Lille only reviews and approves fixed, detailed

17

protocols, we are unable to associate the present registered report with ethics committee

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approval. However, we will submit our registered project to the ethics committee of our

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university once our work has been provisionally accepted by Peer Community In. We will then

20

communicate the ethics committee's decision to Peer Community In. The authors have no

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conflicts interests to declare.

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25

26 **Abstract**

27 Modern professional life is increasingly defined by sedentary office environments. The
28 adoption of sit-stand desks aims to mitigate the risks associated with excessive sitting while
29 enhancing cognitive task performance. Today, the literature reports do not clearly state
30 whether body position (sitting vs. standing) influence physiological and neurobiological
31 adaptations. Furthermore, it is not well-known if the adoption of a standing position is
32 influenced by affective factors, such as anticipated pleasure. This registered report aims to
33 reduce these shortcomings by i) investigating the empirical relationship between body
34 position (sitting vs. standing) and task performance; ii) examining physiological,
35 neurobiological, and affective changes associated with the body positions. Thirty young adults
36 will perform a Posner task in the sitting position and in the standing position. For task
37 performance, reaction time will be collected. To assess the neural mechanisms underlying
38 cognitive processes, hemodynamic responses in dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (DLPFC) will
39 be collected using functional near-infrared spectroscopy (fNIRS). Electrocardiography,
40 electrodermal activity, respiration rate and pulse plethysmography will be recorded using a
41 BIOPAC system. Additionally, participants will complete self-report questionnaires to
42 measure anticipated and remembered pleasure. We expect that standing position will predict a
43 higher task performance, will increase dorsolateral prefrontal cortex oxygenation and heart-
44 rate. Exploratory analyses will test the effect of the body position on affective variables and
45 how affective, psychophysiological and neurobiological responses influence the effects of
46 body position on task performance. These findings will help to move forward on the
47 theoretical understanding of how body position influences task performance, neurobiological,
48 psychophysiological, and affective responses, and how these effects interact with one another.

49 Keywords: body position; task performance; fNIRS; psychophysiological activity; prefrontal
50 activity

51 **Effects of body position on neurobiological, psychophysiological, affective**
52 **and behavioral responses and their interplay: A functional near-infrared**
53 **spectroscopy study**

54 **Introduction**

55 In contemporary societies, sitting has become omnipresent in educational, professional, and
56 domestic environments. Recent data indicate that over half of the world population spends
57 more than 50% of their day sitting (Leitzmann et al., 2018). Among office workers even
58 spend between 65% and 85% of their day sitting in the sitting position (Gupta et al., 2016).
59 Prolonged sedentary behavior is associated with an increased risk of chronic diseases
60 (Ekelund et al., 2016), psychopathological disorders (Wang et al., 2019), and cognitive
61 impairment (Chandrasekaran et al., 2021). Consequently, identifying solutions to reduce
62 sitting time is essential for both preserving public health and maintaining optimal cognitive
63 functions. Among emerging interventions, sit-stand desks have gained global popularity,
64 particularly in Australia, Canada, and the United States (Hall et al., 2019; Zerguine et al.,
65 2021), as an effective means to encourage postural alternation without interruption of work
66 activity (Bonnet & Cheval, 2022). While these devices are more and more adopted to fight the
67 negative effects of sitting too much, it is still unclear i) what is the specific impact of standing
68 (vs. sitting) on cognitive performance and ii) what are the underlying physiological
69 mechanisms.

70 Recent evidence suggests that standing can improve performance in specific cognitive tasks,
71 particularly when measured by fine indicators, such as reaction time. Enhanced performance
72 has been observed in tasks involving the Stroop effect or the Attention Network Test (Abou
73 Khalil et al., 2023, 2024; Rosenbaum et al., 2017; Smith et al., 2019). While van Steenbergen
74 et al. (2024) recently demonstrated that alternating between positions every 20 minutes

75 significantly improves attentional performance and increases arousal while reducing
76 perceived effort, the isolated effect of the body position itself, independent of the alternation,
77 remains under-investigated. At the neurophysiological level, improved task performance
78 while standing is expected to be accompanied by significant physiological changes
79 (Chandrasekaran et al., 2021; Shali et al., 2024; Van Steenbergen et al., 2024). Heart rate
80 variability (HRV), for example, is closely associated with attentional and executive control
81 (Forte et al., 2019) while mean heart rate (HR) and electrodermal activity (EDA) reliably
82 predict cognitive efficiency and vigilance (Solhjoo et al., 2019; Stuldreher et al., 2023). So
83 far, to our knowledge, no study tested relationships between relationships between body
84 position, physiological adaptations and cognitive outcomes. To bridge this gap, using the
85 functional near-infrared spectroscopy (fNIRS) is a relevant technique to examine cortical
86 mechanisms, specifically dorsolateral prefrontal cortex oxygenation, that underlie potential
87 benefits of standing on neurobiological measures.

88 The body position should not only modify physiological, neurobiological and task
89 performance measures but should also impact affective factors. Anticipation of pleasure and
90 memory of past positive experiences are known to predict behavioral change (Asutay &
91 Västfjäll, 2024; Shenhav, 2024). However, it remains unknown how body position, notably
92 within a sit-to-stand paradigm, influences these affective factors to drive behavioral shifts
93 during a cognitive task.

94 In the present framework, we propose an integrative approach that combines behavioral
95 performance, autonomic physiological measures, neurobiological data, and affective factors.
96 While controlling for psychometric profiles and affective factors, this study aims to better
97 understand the cognitive and biological changes induced by changes in body position in a
98 simulated work environment.

99 **Objectives and Hypotheses**

100 Our objectives are to: i) Examine the physiological and neurobiological changes associated
101 with body position ii) Investigate the empirical relationship between body position (sitting vs.
102 standing) and task performance. Our key research question is whether the standing position
103 improves cognitive task performance, increases prefrontal cortex oxygenation, and increases
104 HR.

105

106 Based on literature reports, we assume that (see Table 1):

107 H1: The standing position should increase DLPFC oxygenation.

108 H2: The standing position should result in a higher HR.

109 H3: The standing position should predict higher task performance.

110

111 **Methods**

112 **Participants**

113 Volunteer adults will be eligible if they meet the following criteria: (a) aged 18–30, (b) have
114 normal or corrected-to-normal vision, (c) have no physical issue for maintaining standing
115 balance, and (d) have no motor dysfunction or neurological or psychiatric disorders. The
116 inclusion criteria will be self-reported by the participants. They will be excluded from the
117 study if they do not meet any of the inclusion criteria. Participants will be compensated for
118 their time (i.e., €10 for completing the full procedure). To enhance the representativeness of
119 our sample, we will target university students and young employees from the university. It's
120 unfortunate, but students and workers in university don't yet benefit from ergonomics
121 solutions that help them to stay active.

122 **Study design and Power analysis**

123 The present study will utilize a fully counterbalanced, repeated-measures design. Participants
124 will remain unaware of the study's purpose and hypotheses. Each participant will perform two
125 10-minute blocks for each condition (sitting and standing), resulting in a total task duration of
126 20 minutes per condition and 40 minutes in total. In each condition, participants will complete
127 a Posner task. Before each condition, a baseline of neurobiological and physiological data will
128 be collected over a period of five minutes. The total experiment time will be up to one hour
129 and half, including the time required for fNIRS optode and BIOPAC electrode placement,
130 instructions, and debriefing.

131 We performed an a priori power analysis on R (version 4.5.2) based on the linear mixed-
132 effects models (LMMs) that will be used to test the effect of body position (sitting vs.
133 standing) on, DLPFC oxygenation (H1), HR (H2), and task performance (H3). In fully
134 counterbalanced designs, repeated-measures ANOVA and LMMs are nearly identical in their
135 statistical behavior. This similarity arises because under balanced conditions, the distribution
136 of test statistics under the alternative hypothesis for both approaches follows a noncentral F
137 distribution, with a noncentrality parameter derived from the fixed effects and variance
138 components of the model. For the related equation, see Parma et al. (2023).

139 To guard against the potential overestimation of effect sizes in previous studies, we first
140 applied a safeguard power approach for each hypothesis. This approach calculates the effect
141 size based on the lower bound of a 60% confidence interval from the original findings
142 (Lakens, 2022; Perugini et al., 2014). This conservative method accounts for the uncertainty
143 inherent in the small sample sizes often found in previous reports on which we relied. Using
144 these conservative estimates as fixed effect parameters, we then performed Monte Carlo
145 power simulations (200–250 iterations per step) with the lme4 package in R to determine the
146 required sample size for our linear mixed-effects models (Bates et al., 2015). The simulation
147 parameters for each model were defined as follows:

148 For H1 (DLPFC Oxygenation): Following Rosso et al. (2017), we simulated fNIRS-like noise
149 with a more conservative residual variance ($\sigma^2 = 2.5$) and a random intercept (SD) of 0.80,
150 using a safeguard effect size derived from their reported p-value ($p = 0.008$, $N = 6$).

151 For H2 (HR): Parameters were based on Takayama & Sekiya (2023), who reported a large
152 partial eta-squared ($\eta_p^2 = 0.58$). We utilized a residual variance (σ^2) of 1.2 and a random
153 intercept (SD) of 0.60.

154 For H3 (Task Performance): Data were simulated based on Barra et al. (2015) using a
155 safeguard effect size ($f = 0.21$). The residual variance (σ^2) was set to 1.0 and the random
156 intercept parameter (SD) to 0.50.

157 The required sample size was determined by identifying the minimum number of participants
158 necessary to reach a power of 0.80, with an α level of .05, for the critical fixed effect of the
159 "Condition" (Sitting vs. Standing) in the LMMs. The R code is openly available on Zenodo
160 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18350637>).

161 All these analyses showed that a sample size of 28 participants is required to satisfy the most
162 demanding power requirement among our three primary hypotheses. Any excluded participant
163 will be replaced to maintain a final sample size of 30.

164 **Procedure**

165 Participants will be advised to refrain from consuming caffeine and cigarettes at least 12
166 hours before testing (Heilbronner et al., 2015; Kennedy & Haskell, 2011). Upon arrival,
167 participants will provide written informed consent and self-report sociodemographic data,
168 including age, height, weight, and gender. After being fitted with fNIRS and cardiorespiratory
169 sensors, participants will undergo a five-minute baseline recording in each position (sitting
170 and standing). Each participant will perform two 10-minute blocks for each condition,
171 resulting in a total task duration of 20 minutes per condition and 40 minutes in total. The

172 experimental protocol is fully counterbalanced order to eliminate sequence effects. After each
173 condition, participants will complete self-report questionnaires about their affective
174 experience. The session will conclude with a formal debriefing on the study's objectives.

175 *fNIRS Data.*

176 Cortical activity in the DLPFC will be monitored continuously using the MedelOpt® (Seenel
177 Imaging, Amiens, France) fNIRS system and associated ElOpt software. This fNIRS system
178 offers 16 optodes, divided into 8 light sources (light-emitting diode) and 8 detectors
179 (electropods). The selection of the optimal optode montage for the targeted region of interest
180 (i.e., DLPFC) will be informed by the fOLD toolbox (Zimeo Morais et al., 2018).

181 Specifically, a 10-channel model (eight sources and four detectors), including two short
182 channels (one for each brain hemisphere) will be used (see Figure 1). The sampling frequency
183 will be set at 8 Hz to be able to observe HR in the frequency domain (see Guérin et al., 2026).

184 *Cardiorespiratory Monitoring.*

185 HR and respiratory rate will be continuously recorded using an MP200 system, with a
186 BioNomadix® wearable wireless device PPGED and RSPEC-R modules (BIOPAC Systems,
187 Goleta, USA). Electrocardiography (ECG) electrodes will be placed according to Einthoven's
188 triangle, an imaginary shape formed around the heart (Barold, 2003). Two electrodes will be
189 placed on each collarbone and a third on the rib cage. The respiratory effort transducer will be
190 placed around the chest wall at the sternal level. The sampling frequency will be set to 250
191 Hz. Acquisition of ECG and respiratory data will be facilitated using the AcqKnowledge®
192 software. Regarding HRV, root mean square of successive differences (RMSSD) and standard
193 deviation of normal-to-normal RR intervals (SDNN) time-domain indices will be computed
194 based on ECG data (Laborde et al., 2022). Further details can be found in the "Data Pre-
195 Processing" section.

196 *Behavioral Data.*

197 Task performance will be assessed using reaction times (RT) recorded during a Posner Task.
198 Posner cuing task is employed to measure the orientation of attention by using a cue to orient
199 participants' attention toward a specific spatial location (Posner, 1980). This approach
200 provides a robust measure of attention by comparing response metrics (RT) for valid trials—
201 where the target appears at the cued location—against invalid trials, where the target occurs at
202 an uncued location. This task will serve as the primary metric for testing H3, evaluating the
203 influence of body position on attentional efficiency.

204 *Questionnaires Data.*

205 Remembered pleasure will be measured 5 min after each session using a visual analogy scale
206 ranging from -10 (*very unpleasant*) to +10 (*very pleasant*) in intervals of 1 (Karageorghis et
207 al., 2025). Participants will be asked to answer the following question: “How did the session
208 make you feel?”

209 Anticipated pleasure in relation to a future similar session will be assessed after each session
210 using a visual analogy scale. Participants will be asked to answer the following question:
211 “What affective state do you think you will be in during a future 20-minute standing (or
212 sitting) cognitive task?” (Hutchinson et al., 2023) using the Empirical Valence Scale (Lishner
213 et al., 2008) from 15 empirically spaced verbal anchors, ranging from -100 (*most unpleasant*
214 *imaginable*) to +100 (*most pleasant imaginable*; Zenko et al., 2016).

215 **Data Pre-processing**

216 *fNIRS*

217 To control for the quality of acquired fNIRS data, the power-spectral density will be
218 computed using Welch’s estimation method for each participant, condition and channel. The

219 frequency corresponding to maximal peak in the 60–120 beats per minute (BPM) range will
220 be detected in the power-spectral density of the raw fNIRS data (for a similar procedure, see
221 Pinti et al., 2019). To guarantee that the identified frequency is the genuine HR frequency, it
222 will be compared to the HR measurements provided by the BIOPAC system, with a tolerance
223 threshold of 10 BPM (Guérin et al., 2023). A channel will be excluded if HR frequency is not
224 found in the fNIRS signals. An entire participant's data set will be removed prior to further
225 analyses if all channels pertaining to the region of interest (ROI) is excluded. Any excluded
226 participants will be replaced to ensure that $N = 30$.

227 The presence of the heart pulse is a necessary but not sufficient condition to ensure the quality
228 of fNIRS data (Pollonini et al., 2016). Thus, the QT-NIRS toolbox (Quality Testing of Near-
229 Infrared Scans; Hernandez & Pollonini, 2020) will be used to identify channels with poor
230 optical coupling through the computation of the scalp-coupling index (cardiac filter = 0.5-2.5
231 Hz; time window = 5 s). For a given participant and channel, fNIRS signals characterized by a
232 scalp-coupling index < 0.7 for at least 10% of the time will be removed prior to further
233 analyses. As for the power-spectral density check, a participant's entire data set will be
234 removed prior to further analyses if all channels pertaining to the ROI are excluded.

235 For the two brain hemispheres, the data coming from the corresponding short channel will be
236 regressed from the collected fNIRS signals from regular channels to account for noncortical
237 hemodynamic responses that represent potential confounds.

238 Correction for motion artefacts will be performed using wavelet filtering (interquartile range
239 = 0.5) in Homer 3 (v1.58.0; Massachusetts General Hospital, Boston, MA). The motion-
240 corrected data will be visually inspected to ensure that the selected interquartile range value is
241 well suited to the fNIRS data. For a given participant, visual inspection will be performed to
242 ensure that no motion artefacts are still visible in the signal (i.e., high-frequency spikes

243 and/or baseline shifts). To reject both cardiac and breathing rates along with parts of Mayer
244 oscillations, a lowpass filter set at 0.1 Hz will be applied.

245 Prior to each experimental block, a 3-minute resting baseline (B) will be recorded. During this
246 period, participants will be instructed to remain immobile with their eyes closed and to clear
247 their minds while fNIRS and ECG data are simultaneously acquired. For each condition, the
248 plateau (P) will be defined as the mean values of oxygenated hemoglobin (HbO₂) upon a 5-s
249 time window starting at the beginning of the condition and upon the last 5 s of the condition,
250 respectively. To estimate the amplitude of changes in oxygenation during a condition, the
251 variations ΔHbO_2 will be given relative to its baseline (i.e., by subtracting B to P).

252 *Electrocardiography*

253 To ensure accurate extraction of cardiac metrics, raw ECG signals will be pre-processed on
254 Python (v. 3.13.7) using a systematic pipeline designed to minimize noise and artifacts while
255 preserving physiological fidelity. A 50 Hz Butterworth notch filter will be applied to
256 eliminate electrical line interference. Signal conditioning will be performed using a 1.0 Hz
257 high-pass finite impulse response (FIR) filter (order = 2) to remove baseline wander and low-
258 frequency artifacts (Nguyen et al., 2021). Then, a 30 Hz low-pass FIR filter (order = 2) will
259 be applied to attenuate high-frequency noise, in line with established protocols (Hu et al.,
260 2020). R-peaks will be identified based on a benchmarking using neurokit, pantompkins1985,
261 hamilton2002, and emrich2023 methods on Python. Therefore, a Visibility Graph-Based
262 Detection method will be used (Emrich et al., 2023; Koka & Muma, 2022).

263 The HR will be extracted using the `nk.signal_rate` function from the neurokit2 Python library
264 (Makowski et al., 2021), which computes the instantaneous heart rate in BPM based on the
265 intervals between detected R-peaks. The HRV (RMSSD and SDNN) will be extracted using

266 the nk.hrv_time function, which computes time-domain HRV metrics from the R-peak
267 intervals.

268 *Respiratory Rate*

269 The respiratory signal will be resampled to 50 Hz using a fast Fourier transform based method
270 (Cole & Voytek, 2019). This resampling rate is appropriate as it is sufficient to capture
271 respiratory dynamics without unnecessary computational overhead (BIOPAC Systems, Inc.,
272 n.d.). A second-order Butterworth bandpass filter (0.05–1 Hz) will be applied to isolate the
273 respiratory frequency band (BIOPAC Systems, Inc., n.d.). This range will be selected to
274 capture typical respiratory rates (0.06–0.6 breaths per second, equivalent to 3.6–36 breaths per
275 minute; Ansari et al., 2009; Braun, 1990).

276 *Behavioral Data*

277 Behavioral performance during the Posner cuing task will be assessed using reaction times
278 (RT). Only correct trials will be included in the analyses; trials with incorrect responses or
279 missing data will be discarded. To ensure the robustness of the temporal data, trials deviating
280 by more than 2.5 standard deviations from the individual mean will be removed to account for
281 attention lapses. RTs shorter than 150 ms (anticipations) or longer than 1000 ms (late
282 responses) will be excluded. For each participant, mean RTs will be calculated separately for
283 each experimental condition (sitting vs. standing) and trial type (valid vs. invalid cues). RT
284 scores will be averaged across the two 10-minute blocks per condition to provide a stable
285 measure of attentional performance.

286 **Statistical Analyses**

287 *Main Analyses*

288 After conducting descriptive analyses, we will compute LMMs with associated contrasts
289 across conditions to test H1–3. Dependent variables will include preprocessed Δ scores for
290 neurobiological and psychophysiological measures (H1 and H2) and mean RT for task
291 performance (H3). All scores will be averaged over the two 10-minute blocks assigned to
292 each condition (sitting and standing). The conditions will be specified in the LMM as the
293 fixed factor, and the participants will be specified as the random factor. We will build and fit
294 the LMMs using restricted maximum likelihood estimation with the lme4 R package (Bates et
295 al., 2015). P-values will be approximated using Satterthwaite's method to estimate degrees of
296 freedom and provide accurate p-values for fixed effects in models with complex random
297 effects structures (lmerTest package; Kuznetsova, 2016; Parma et al., 2023). Effect sizes for
298 fixed effects will be reported using marginal pseudo R^2 , computed with the MuMIn package
299 (Barton, 2018).

300 If no significant differences are found, two one-sided t tests (TOSTs) will be performed to test
301 for equivalence between the two conditions for each variable (Lakens et al., 2018). The
302 equivalence margins for the TOSTs will be based on the smallest effect size of interest
303 (SESOI; Lakens et al., 2018). The lower (ΔL) and upper (ΔU) bounds will be set as
304 symmetric around zero, defined as $\Delta L = -\text{SESOI}$ and $\Delta U = +\text{SESOI}$. To determine the
305 SESOI, a safeguard power approach will be used (Perugini et al., 2014), which sets the
306 margins to the lower bound of the 60% confidence interval of previous findings. Specifically,
307 the following equivalence margins will be used:

308 For H1 (DLPFC Oxygenation): $\Delta L = -0.17$ and $\Delta U = 0.17$. These bounds correspond to the
309 safeguard estimate calculated from the findings of Rosso et al. (2017), accounting for the
310 inherent noise in fNIRS measurements.

311 For H2 (HR): $\Delta L = -1.25$ and $\Delta U = 1.25$. Given the large effects observed in physiological
312 arousal by Takayama & Sekiya (2023), these margins ensure a conservative test of
313 equivalence for heart-rate variations between positions.

314 For H3 (Task Performance): $\Delta L = -0.21$ and $\Delta U = 0.21$. These margins are based on the
315 safeguard effect size derived from Barra et al. (2015), representing the smallest plausible
316 effect size of interest for behavioral performance.

317 Statistical assumptions of normality of the residuals, linearity, multicollinearity and undue
318 influence will be checked for all models using the performance R package (Lüdtke et al.,
319 2021). In the event of a violation of normality, the data will undergo a normalisation process
320 that will be contingent on the data distribution curves in question (e.g., log10, cube root).

321 Exploratory analyses will also be conducted on EDA and pulse plethysmography (PPG) to
322 provide supplementary insights.

323 **Anticipated Timeline for Completion of the Proposed set of Studies**

324 If this contribution is accepted for publication, data collection will take place in January 2027
325 over a period of five months. We estimate that pre-processing and data analyses will take a
326 further three months (a total of nine months). Accordingly, we expect to submit the Stage 2
327 within 9 months after beginning data collection.

328

329 **Open Practices**

330 Stage 1 analysis codes have been made publicly available on Zenodo

331 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18350636>). The final dataset, codes and research materials

332 will be made available at the point of Stage 2 submission.

333 **CRedit Author Statement**

334 Paul Butin: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology,

335 Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision,

336 Software.

337 Layan Fessler: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Writing –

338 review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software.

339 Cédric T. Bonnet: Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration,

340 Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision,

341 Software, Resources, Funding acquisition.

342

343 **Acronyms**

344 **BPM:** Beats per minute

345 **DLPFC:** Dorsolateral prefrontal cortex

346 **ECG:** Electrocardiography

347 **EDA:** Electrodermal activity

348 **FIR:** Finite impulse response

349 **fNIRS:** Functional near-infrared spectroscopy

350 **HbO₂:** Oxygenated hemoglobin

351 **HR:** Heart rate

352 **HRV:** Heart rate variability

353 **PPG:** Pulse plethysmography

354 **LMM:** Linear mixed model

355 **RMSSD:** Root mean square of successive differences

356 **ROI:** Region of interest

357 **RT:** Reaction time

358 **SDNN:** Standard deviation of normal-to-normal RR intervals

359 **SESOI:** Smallest effect size of interest

360 **TOSTs:** Two one-sided t tests for equivalence

361

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Table 1: Study Design

<i>Question</i>	<i>Hypothesis</i>	<i>Sampling plan</i>	<i>Analysis plan</i>	<i>Rationale for deciding the sensitivity</i>	<i>Interpretation given different outcomes</i>	<i>Theory that could be shown wrong</i>
Could standing lead to a higher cortical oxygenation in the DLPFC compared to sitting?	Mean ΔHbO_2 : Sitting < Standing (H1).	N =22; $\alpha=.05$; 1- $\beta=.80$	LMMs with Position as fixed factor and Participants as random factor. TOSTs if non-significant.	Equivalence bounds: $\Delta L = -0.17$, $\Delta U = 0.17$.	Supported: $p < .050$ and difference in predicted direction. Equivalent: $p < .050$ for both TOSTs.	Failure to confirm H1 would call into question the claim that standing position increases cortical oxygenation in the DLPFC.
Does the standing position result in a higher heart rate (HR) compared to the sitting position?	Mean HR: Sitting < Standing (H2).	N =10; $\alpha=.05$; 1- $\beta=.80$	LMMs with Position as fixed factor and Participants as random factor. TOSTs if non-significant.	Equivalence bounds: $\Delta L = -1.25$, $\Delta U = 1.25$.	Supported: $p < .050$ and difference in predicted direction. Equivalent: $p < .050$ for both TOSTs	Failure to confirm H2 would call into question the expected increase in autonomic arousal associated with the standing posture.
Does standing position improve attentional efficiency?	Mean RT: Sitting > Standing (H3).	N = 28; $\alpha=.05$; 1- $\beta=.80$	LMMs with Position as fixed factor and Participants as random factor. Data cleaned for lapses (> 2.5 SD). TOSTs if non-significant.	Equivalence bounds: $\Delta L = -0.21$, $\Delta U = 0.21$.	Supported: $p < .050$ and difference in predicted direction. Equivalent: $p < .050$ for both TOSTs	Failure to confirm H3 would call into question the theory that the standing posture enhances attentional efficiency and task performance.

Figure 1

Diagrammatic Representation of the fNIRS optodes' location (red: source; blue: detector)

